

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH EMPLOYMENT OUTCOMES OF COOKERY NC II GRADUATES OF TESDA SCHOOLS IN EASTERN SAMAR

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ABSTRACT

This associational study aimed to answer the following objectives: to identify the competencies of trainees; to determine the profile of trainers; to determine the profile of the school; to determine the employment outcomes of Cookery NC-II graduates; to find out if there is a significant relationship between competencies of trainees towards the employment outcomes of graduates; to establish if there is a significant relationship between competencies of trainers towards the employment outcomes of graduates; to gauge if there is a significant relationship between the profile of the school towards the employment outcomes of graduates. Using a self-structured survey instrument, the findings of the study revealed that there was a significant, positive correlation between the nature of employment and common competencies; not significant, positive correlation between nature of employment and the adequacy of school resources and the qualification of trainers; significant, positive correlation between wage and the core competencies of trainees; not significant, positive correlation between wage and the qualification of trainers; not significant; negative correlation between tenure and the adequacy of school resources; not significant, positive correlation between tenure and the curriculum; significant, positive correlation between position and common competencies; significant, positive correlation between tenure and the basic competencies; not significant, positive correlation between the nature of employment and the adequacy of school resources; not significant, negative correlation between tenure and wage and the adequacy of school resources; and not significant, positive correlation between school resources and the trainings attended by the trainers and the wage of the trainees.

Keywords: *Employment outcomes, employment status, technical vocational education and training, technical competence, school resources, blue desk jobs bridging*

INTRODUCTION

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2010) considers vocational training in capacitating human assets and capabilities, especially the poor and vulnerable people who have less opportunity for higher education. In the present, Rwanda is facing problem on unqualified people in the workforce, particularly in the technical sectors (Ministry of Education of Rwanda, 2008).

The 4th Note Series of the Afghanistan Gender Mainstreaming Implementation stressed out that unemployment is a problem for all young people in Afghanistan. In addition, the International Labour Organization reported Afghanistan with the highest level of unemployment with predominantly young population. According to Baselala (2010), the informal sector dominates the labour market in the Pacific Islands countries, hence the (TVET) is considered second class and is not given the recognition it deserves causing skills shortage and underdevelopment in the private sector.

According to Barlongo (2015) the newly implemented K to 12 Program ensures that country will produce competent graduates that will serve as the backbone for a highly skilled and employable work force. This move, hoped to give more chances of getting employed in blue-collar work. Syjuco (2009) noted that non-formal education capacitates of giving out education opportunities especially to those who cannot avail formal education.

Barlongo stressed out that the Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) sector provides education and training opportunities that prepare students and other clients for employment. The International Labor Organization (2012) identifies three sources that demand for TVET in the Philippines including the country's priority sectors, its need to replace skills lost to labour migration, and the mismatching of domestic labour market for supply and demand. On the other side, Baselala (2010) noted that TVET sector faces multitude of challenges requiring careful scrutiny and attention including domestic job opportunities and deployment of Overseas Filipino Workers.

The results of the January 2018 LFS bolstered by employment gains in the services (3.8% or 847,000 jobs) and industry sectors (10.5% or 719,000 jobs). Likewise, unemployment rate eased at 5.3 percent from 6.6 percent, the lowest unemployment rate recorded for all LFS January rounds in the past decade. Furthermore, the Department of Labor and Employment reported that the underemployment rate increased notably by 1.7 percentage points (ppts) from 16.3 percent to 18.0 percent, which warrants a national concern.

The aforementioned statements indicate that trainers' competence and personal characteristics are essentials in ensuring positive employment outcomes.

To comply with TVET requirements, the TESDA, its lead agency should provide quality and efficient technical skills development to the Filipino people as embodied in Section 2 of the TESDA Act of 1994.

The findings of this study aided the authority in regularly monitoring and assessing effectiveness of TVET provisions based on the employment outcomes of its graduates that will serve as a feedback mechanism on the status of implementation of major TVET policies and

programs. Furthermore, this study is expected to find out which among the variables relate with employment outcomes of Cookery NC II graduates.

Research Questions

The study investigated the factors associated with employment outcomes of Cookery NC II graduates of TESDA Schools in Eastern Samar. Specifically, the study aimed to attain the following objectives:

1. To identify the competencies of trainees in terms of:
 - 1.1 basic competencies,
 - 1.2 common competencies, and
 - 1.3 core competencies.
2. To determine the profile of trainers in terms of:
 - 2.1 technical competence, and
 - 2.2 attitude towards teaching.
3. To determine the profile of the school in terms:
 - 3.1 resources,
 - 3.2 curriculum, and
 - 3.3 blue desk jobs bridging.
4. To determine the employment outcomes of Cookery NC-II graduates in terms of:
 - 4.1 employment status
 - 4.1.1 nature of employment,
 - 4.1.2 tenure,
 - 4.1.3 position, and
 - 4.1.4 wage.
5. To find out if there is a significant relationship between competencies of trainees towards the employment outcomes of Cookery NC-II graduates.
6. To establish if there is a significant relationship between competencies of trainers towards the employment outcomes of Cookery NC-II graduates.
7. To gauge if there is a significant relationship between the profile of the school towards the employment outcomes of Cookery NC-II graduates.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the associational research design was used to determine relationship or association between competencies of trainees and employment outcomes of graduates; trainers competencies and employment outcomes of graduates; and school profile and employment outcomes of graduates.

This study was conducted in three (3) TESDA Training Institutions in Eastern Samar namely: Arteche National Agricultural School (ANAS) in the municipality of Arteche, Balangiga National Agricultural School (BNAS) in Balangiga, and Samar National School of Arts and Trades (SNSAT), in Taft, Eastern Samar. These schools operate under the supervision of the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA).

Three groups of respondents were involved in this study, namely, trainees who finished Cookery NC II, Trainers of Cookery NC II, and Blue Desk Focal. Unrestricted random sampling

using lottery technique was used in this study. A list of graduates from each school was generated and numbered accordingly in ascending order starting from number 1. Numbers corresponding the respondent was written in a small sheet of paper. The numbered sheets of paper was rolled and mixed thoroughly. The rolled papers were drawn from the box one at a time until the computed sample size is reached per school. The number that corresponds the name in the list was checked to note that it is included in the sample.

This study employed three survey instruments: for trainees, trainers, and blue desk focal. Though, some parts of the instrument have been lifted from previous researches, there has been some modifications made, therefore this has been pre-tested to determine the comprehensibility of each item and to test the applicability of said items to the respondents and other aspects like validity and reliability. The survey instrument for trainees was composed of four parts; part A is employment status, part B is on competencies, part C is on adequacy of school resources and part D on curriculum. The instrument for trainers was divided into three parts; part A on technical competence, part B on attitude towards teaching. Technical competence is subdivided into three components; educational background, trainings attended, and TVET trainer's qualification. For part B, trainers indicated how they feel about teaching as a career, using a 5-point Likert scale. The survey instrument for blue desk focal was composed of eight-item questionnaire to measure the extent of the schools implementation of the blue desk jobs bridging program and jobs placement program.

To generate meaningful results of the data collected and for interpretation and discussions, the study employed both descriptive and inferential analysis. The descriptive aspect of analysis focused on univariate analysis through the use of measures of central tendency such as the mean and mode, computation of percentages and identification of frequencies. The inferential aspect dealt on bivariate analysis in determining relationships or association of variables under investigation. Depending on the scale of measurement of data, the following statistical tools were used in the different approaches of data analysis: Spearman's rank order correlation test, Kendall's tau-b test, a Chi-square test for association. Hypothesis testing was set at 5% level of significance and corresponding 95% confidence interval.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study identified the competencies of trainees in terms of three units of competencies namely: basic competencies, common competencies, and core competencies. A self-structured instrument was used to measure the level of competencies of respondents.

As reflected in Table 2, the trainee respondents' level of competence on all units of competency of Cookery NC II as described by an aggregate mode of 5 was interpreted as high level of competence. This result implies that the graduates were confident enough in performing the specified units of competencies.

Table 2. Competencies of trainee-respondents

Units of Competency	Mode	Interpretation
BASIC COMPETENCIES		
Participating in workplace communication	5	High Level of Competence
Working in a team environment	5	High Level of Competence
Practicing career professionalism	5	High Level of Competence
Practicing occupational health and safety procedures	5	High Level of Competence
Aggregate Mode	5	High Level of Competence
COMMON COMPETENCIES		
Developing and updating industry knowledge	5	High Level of Competence
Observing workplace hygiene procedures	5	High Level of Competence
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1. Performing computer operations		
Performing workplace and safety practices	5	High Level of Competence
Providing effective customer service	5	High Level of Competence
Aggregate Mode	5	High Level of Competence
CORE COMPETENCIES		
Cleaning and maintaining kitchen premises	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing stocks, sauces and soups	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing appetizers	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing salads and dressing	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing sandwiches	5	High Level of Competence
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2. Preparing meat dishes		
Preparing vegetables dishes	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing egg dishes	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing starch dishes	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing poultry and game dish(es)	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing seafood dishes	5	High Level of Competence
Preparing desserts	5	High Level of Competence
Packaging prepared food	5	High Level of Competence
Aggregate Mode	5	High Level of Competence

Trainers Profile

Table 3 shows that 66.7% of the trainers were graduates of 4 to 5 years Technical and the computed mean of 1.67 indicates that they have moderate level of competence in terms of educational background. For relevant local trainings attended, the trainers have an average level of competence having a computed mean of 1.50 for having attended four trainings on beginner level. Fifty percent of those who attended an intermediate level of local training have a moderately level of competence with the computed mean of 2.0. The trainers who attended an advanced local training have an average level of competence with 1.67 computed mean. Those who attended relevant foreign training has an average level of competence with computed mean of 1.0. This result implies that trainers' level of competence needs to be improved by pursuing graduate studies relevant to the baccalaureate technical course and they should also attend local and foreign training relevant to their specialization on higher proficiency level.

Table 3. Profile of trainers in terms of technical competence

Technical Competence	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Interpretation
Educational Background				
Graduate of 3-year Technical Course + Education	2	33.3		
Graduate of 4-5 years Technical course	4	66.7	1.67	Moderate Level of Competence
<i>Total</i>	6	100%		
Trainings Attended				
Relevant Local Trainings				
Proficiency Level:				
<i>Beginner</i>				
<1	4	66.7 %		
2	1	16.7 %	1.50	Average Level of Competence
3-4	1	16.7 %		
<i>Intermediate</i>				
<1	3	50 %	2	Moderately Level of Competence
2	0			
3-4	3	50 %		
<i>Advanced</i>				
<1	4	66.7 %		
2	0		1.67	Average Level of Competence
3-4	2	33.3 %		
Relevant Foreign Trainings				
<i>Intermediate</i>				
3-4	1	16.7	1	Average Level of Competence
TVET Trainers Qualification				
NC IIs				
1	4	67.6		
2	1	16.7	2	Moderate Level of Competence
3>	1	16.7		

Table 4 shows that trainer respondents agree on 19 items depicting their attitude towards teaching as described by 4 mode while they strongly agree on the item, "I am convinced of the importance

of teaching” item with 5 mode. This result implies that the trainer respondents, no matter how diverse they are in some aspects, still value the importance of teaching and is convinced about it.

Table 4. Profile of Trainers in terms of their attitude towards teaching

Attitude towards teaching	Mode	Interpretation
Teaching is the best job I can think of.	4	Agree
There are a lot of advantages in teaching.	4	Agree
I do care for the work of a teacher	4	Agree
Teaching would be a wonderful occupation to anyone.	4	Agree
Teaching is all right for me but not for some people.	4	Agree
I am convinced of the importance of teaching.	5	Strongly Agree
Teaching as a career is worth the sacrifice of going to college.	4	Agree
I am sure I would enjoy teaching.	4	Agree
Teaching is as good job as any.	4	Agree
There are more advantages then disadvantages to teaching as a career.	4	Agree
I would be willing to take any job related to teaching.	4	Agree
Teaching is the most interesting of all professions.	4	Agree
Teaching is also another means of existing.	4	Agree
Modern teaching is as good as 20 years ago.	4	Agree
Teaching is a means of self-expression.	4	Agree
Teaching offers some activities for advancement.	4	Agree
Teaching is not a monotonous occupation.	4	Agree
Some teachers are not fit for such a responsible position.	4	Agree
The teachers largely help on the intellectual standards of a country.	4	Agree
Too many teachers like to teach but cannot.	4	Agree

School Profile

Table 5 shows that the library facilities and the support facilities (medical clinic, sports facilities) in the respondent schools were present but limited in space or number. Classrooms, workshops, and school building were sufficient in space and number. The grand mean of 2.51 is interpreted as present or sufficient space or number. This result implies that other school resources are present but of limited space or number, particularly medical clinic, sports facilities, and library.

Table 5. Profile of the school in terms of resources

Resources	Mean	Interpretation
Classrooms	2.81	Present or sufficient space or number
Workshops/Laboratory Room	2.75	Present or sufficient space or number
Library Facilities	2.13	Present but limited space or number
Support Facilities (medical clinic, sports facilities)	2.10	Present but limited space or number
School Building	2.75	Present or sufficient space or number
GRAND MEAN	2.51	Present or sufficient space or number

It can be gleaned from Table 6 that the grand mean score of all the conditions related to curriculum is 2.85 interpreted as very much provided and satisfying. All the conditions are very much provided and satisfying. This result implies that as perceived by the trainees, Cookery NC II is in demand; the length of study is adequate to develop skills required; more practical work; and it offers immediate work for their graduates.

Table 6. Profile of the school in terms of curriculum

CONDITIONS	Mean	Interpretation
The course Cookery NC II is very much in demand at the present times, whether in the local, provincial, regional, national or international market.	2.86	Very much provided and satisfying
The lengths of time for studying the courses offered in this school are adequate to develop the specific skills required for the course.	2.86	Very much provided and satisfying
The courses in this school require their students to have more practical work or laboratory to prepare them for their working life ahead.	2.86	Very much provided and satisfying
The courses in this school are designed to promote the establishment of close school-community partnership where teachers and administrators work cooperatively with the business community for the conduct of educational trips or on-the-job training for the students	2.84	Very much provided and satisfying
The courses in this school offer immediate work for their graduates either through self-employment or in the business establishments within and outside the locality.	2.84	Very much provided and satisfying

GRAND MEAN	2.85	Very much provided and satisfying
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Table 7 presents that all the three schools found the baker, cook and waiter jobs on either industry forum or online job sites. Two schools found bartending jobs, and only one school found domestic helper and food processing personnel jobs. It can be gleaned further that most schools find the identified jobs thru online job sites. This result implies that employers are utilizing the information superhighway in advertising their job vacancies. Aside from being economical, the Internet technology and the social media is able to produce and advertise employment opportunities.

Table 7. Job opportunities per job search strategy used

Job Title	Job Opportunities		Job Search Strategy Used			
	Frequency	Percentage	<i>Industry Forum & FGD</i>		<i>Online Job Sites</i>	
			<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Baker	3	100	1	33.3	2	66.7
Bartender	2	66.6			2	100
Cook	3	100	1	33.3	2	66.7
Domestic Helper	1	33.3			1	33.3
Food Processing Personnel	1	33.3	1	33.3		
Waiter	3	100	1	33.3	2	66.7

Employment Outcomes of Cookery NC II Graduates

The employment outcomes of Cookery NC II graduates were categorized into employment status, nature of employment, tenure, position, and wage.

Out of 246 respondents of the study, 125 were employed and 121 unemployed. The following data reveals the characteristics of the employed group.

Table 8. Employment outcomes of the respondents

Status of Employment	Frequency	Percentage
Nature of Employment		
Permanent	10	8
Contractual	59	47.2

	Job Order	56	44.8
	<i>Total</i>	125	100%
Tenure	< one year	106	84.8
	1 -2 years	7	5.6
	2 - 4 years	4	3.2
	> 5 years	8	6.4
	<i>Total</i>	125	100%
Position	Trainee	81	64.8
	Employee	44	35.2
	<i>Total</i>	125	100%
Wage	1,000 – 3,000/month	81	64.8
	4,000 – 6,000/month	28	22.4
	7,000 – 10,000/month	6	4.8
	more than 10,000	10	8
	<i>Total</i>	125	100%

Table 8 shows that 47.2% of the employed graduates are on contractual basis and only 8% are permanent. One hundred six or 84.8% of those employed have worked for less than a year. Only 35.2% are considered employees, most of them (64.8%) are trainee category. Eighty one (64.8%) of the employed graduates have received a wage ranging from 1,000 - 3,000/month. Only 8% received a wage of more than 10,000/month.

Relationship between the Trainees' Competencies and Employment Outcomes of Graduates

Using the Chi-square test for association between nature of employment and the competencies of trainees, the result revealed a high, positive correlation between the nature of employment and common competencies, which was statistically significant. ($X^2 = .746, p = .047$). This result implies that the trainees' nature of employment affects the delivery of common competencies. Trainees who are not yet permanently employed performed less compared to those who are regularly employed most specially on common competencies. This is a manifestation of the tantamount unemployment rate in the country that greatly affects the work force and the industry as a whole. This result is related to that of Thompson and Pearce (1990) findings, who both asserted serious doubts seated to trainees experiences and qualifications as it indicates failure to use highly caliber assessors and narrowness in the skills required for qualification. This result is due to the fact that in rural areas, employment is mainly of the casual nature, often over a period of a few months, not necessarily in the field of specialization.

The same test was used for the association between position and the competencies of trainees, the result revealed a moderate, positive correlation between position and common competencies, which was statistically significant. ($X^2 = .427, p = .013$). This result implies that when a trainee earns a higher position, s/he is immersed with the actual common competencies needed for his own growth, therefore fully realizing the importance of these competencies. The trainee's performance satisfies the job requirement; hence high quality standards are met. Felstead (2011), assumed that raising skill levels improved work practices and employee's

commitment to work. Furthermore, he explained that when an employer gives workers the tools and abilities to take on more responsibilities, the employee learns more on production processes in order to make meaningful suggestions. This finding substantiates the need for improvement in the employee's performance and redefining the appraisal mechanisms for workers.

To test the relationship between tenure and the competencies of trainees, Spearman's rank order correlation was used. There was a moderate, positive correlation between tenure and the basic competencies which was statistically significant ($r_s = .609, p=.029$). This result implies that the trainees' learning gained from basic competencies affects their chance of getting security of tenure. Skewes et al. (2018) showed in their research that self-determination and relational determination via informational competence enabled the subjects to attuned with different paths to self-determination and identity in the workplace. This informational competence related to basic competencies has an effect on the tenure of a trainee.

Finally, Kendall's tau-b test for correlation was used in exploring the relationship between the wage and the competencies of trainees. The result revealed a low, positive correlation between wage and the core competencies of trainees which was statistically significant ($T_b = .350, p=.033$). The empirical result shows that the variation of wages can be explained by the core competencies in which the former affects the latter. Abaida et al (n.d.) resolves that the labor market rewards less specialized competencies; they contend that methodological competence was deemed necessary than cognitive skills.

Table 9. Test of relationship between competencies of trainees towards the employment outcomes of Cookery NC II graduates

Correlates (n=125)	Basic Competencies		Common Competencies		Core Competencies	
	Result	Interpretation	Result	Interpretation	Result	Interpretation
Nature of Employment	$X^2 = .458$	Moderate Correlation	$X^2 = .746$	High Correlation	$X^2 = .940$	Very High Correlation
	$p = .261$	Not Significant	$p = .047$	Significant	$p = .455$	Not Significant
Tenure	$r_s = .609$	Moderate Correlation	$r_s = .362$	Low Correlation	$r_s = -.433$	Moderate Correlation
	$p = .029$	Significant	$p = .548$	Not Significant	$p = -.140$	Not Significant
Position	$X^2 = .337$	Low Correlation	$X^2 = .427$	Moderate Correlation	$X^2 = .542$	Moderate Correlation
	$p = .335$	Not Significant	$p = .013$	Significant	$p = .211$	Not Significant

	Tb= .239	Low Correlation	Tb = .333	Low Correlation	Tb = .350	Low Correlation	*tested at 0.05 (two-tailed)
Wage	p = .178	Not Significant	p =.468	Not Significant	p =.033	Significant	

Relationship between the Trainers and the Employment Outcomes of Cookery NC II Graduates

Chi-square test for association was run to examine the relationship between employment outcomes and the qualification of trainers, the result revealed a low, positive correlation between the nature of employment and the qualification of trainers which was statistically not significant. ($X^2 = .246, p=.102$). This result implies the trainers' nature of employment does not affect their individual qualifications. Hence, trainers should be submitting themselves to a regular trainings and seminars to improve their performance in the workplace. The result however is opposed in the findings made by Loch et. al (2000) who asserted that status competition greatly enhances the employees' performance in the workplace. The association between the nature of employment and the trainings attended by the trainers revealed a low, positive correlation and was statistically not significant. ($X^2 = .237, p=.326$). This result implies that the frequency of trainers' attending trainings does not affect their respective nature of employment.

To test the relationship between tenure of trainees and the qualification of trainers, Spearman's rank order correlation was used. There was a moderate, negative correlation between tenure and the adequacy of school resources which was statistically not significant ($r_s = -.483, p=.350$). This result implies that the trainers tenure of service is not related to availability of school resources. Likewise, tenure and the trainings attended by the trainers was correlated and it revealed that there was a low, positive correlation which was statistically not significant ($r_s = .237, p=.326$). This result implies that the trainers' tenure is related to the number of trainings attended. Enabling them to share concepts and relate competencies to the ever-changing society.

To test the association of the trainees' employment outcomes and the trainers competencies, Kendall's tau-b test for correlation was used. The result revealed a low, positive correlation between wage and the qualification of trainers which was statistically not significant ($Tb = .383, p=.206$). This result implies that the trainers' wage does not affect the qualifications set on them. Same test was run to check the relationship between the trainings attended by the trainers and the wage of the trainees and the result showed a moderate, positive correlation which was statistically not significant ($Tb = .656, p=.106$). This result implies that the trainers' wage is not affected by the frequency of trainings they have attended.

Table 10. Test of relationship between Competencies of Trainers towards the

Employment Outcomes of Cookery NC II graduates

Correlates	Trainers Competencies			
	Qualification		Training Attended	
	Result	Interpretation	Result	Interpretation
Nature of Employment	$X^2 = .246$	Low Correlation	$X^2 = .237$	Low Correlation
	$p = .102$	Not Significant	$p = .326$	Not Significant
Tenure	$rs = -.483$	Moderate Correlation	$rs = .418$	Moderate Correlation
	$p = .350$	Not Significant	$p = .224$	Not Significant
Position	$X^2 = .476$	Moderate Correlation	$X^2 = .256$	Low Correlation
	$p = .125$	Not Significant	$p = .345$	Significant
Wage	$Tb = -.383$	Low Correlation	$Tb = .656$	Moderate Correlation
	$p = .206$	Not Significant	$p = .106$	Not Significant

*tested at 0.05 (two-tailed)

Relationship between the Profile of the School and the Employment Outcomes of Cookery NC II Graduates

Utilizing Chi-square test for association between the school profile and the nature of employment, the result revealed a moderate, positive correlation between the nature of employment and the adequacy of school resources, which was statistically not significant. ($X^2 = .404$, $p = .255$). This result implies that the trainers' nature of employment is not affected by the status of school's resources. Trainers may use technological innovations like a projected instruction based learning and modular type of instruction.

The same test was used for the association between nature of employment and the adequacy of school resources, the result revealed a low, positive correlation, which was statistically not significant. ($X^2 = .233$, $p = .136$). This result implies the trainer's nature of employment has nothing to do with the availability of school resources. This result indicates that TESDA is not experiencing problems on inadequacy of learning resources.

To test the relationship between tenure and the school profile, Spearman's rank order correlation was used. There was a negligible, negative correlation between tenure and the adequacy of school resources which was statistically not significant ($rs = .181$, $p = .770$). This

result implies that the as the trainers' years in service increases his need for school resources decreases. Likewise, tenure and the curriculum of the school was correlated and it revealed that there was a moderate, positive correlation which was statistically not significant ($r_s = .612$, $p = .272$). This result implies that the trainers' tenure does not affect his curriculum perspective. This ensures that the trainers are working on their own professional development.

To test the association of the school profile and the trainees' employment outcomes, Kendall's tau-b test for correlation was used. The result revealed a negligible, negative correlation between wage and the adequacy of school resources which was statistically not significant ($T_b = .167$, $p = .717$). This result implies that since TESDA is providing all the materials for the trainers, their wages are not put on stake. Same test was run to check the relationship between the school curriculum and the wage of the trainers and the result showed a moderate, positive correlation between wage and the school curriculum which was statistically not significant ($T_b = .612$, $p = .221$). This result implies since a well prepared curricular framework is well provided, the trainers are not having any problem with partaking an amount on developing one.

Table 11. Test of relationship between the school profile towards the employment outcomes of Cookery NC II graduates

Correlates Employment Outcomes	School Profile			
	Adequacy of Resources		Curriculum	
	Result	Interpretation	Result	Interpretation
Nature of Employment	$X^2 = .404$	Moderate Correlation	$X^2 = .233$	Low Correlation
	$p = .255$	Not Significant	$p = .136$	Not Significant
Tenure	$r_s = -.181$	Negligible Correlation	$r_s = .612$	Moderate Correlation
Position	$p = .770$	Not Significant	$p = .272$	Not Significant
	$X^2 = .566$	Moderate Correlation	$X^2 = .819$	High Correlation
Wage	$p = .425$	Not Significant	$p = .035$	Significant
	$T_b = -.167$	Negligible Correlation	$T_b = .612$	Moderate Correlation
	$p = .717$	Not Significant	$p = .221$	Not Significant

*tested at 0.05 (two-tailed)

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: Cookery NC II graduates of TESDA Schools in Eastern Samar were highly competent, Cookery NC II trainers have moderate level of competence in terms of educational background and average level of competence in terms of trainings attended, TESDA Schools in Eastern Samar offering Cookery NC II qualification have a “sufficient space or number” in terms of resources and their curriculum is “very much provided and satisfying”, There was a high, positive correlation between the nature of employment and common competencies; moderate, positive correlation between position and common competencies; moderate, positive correlation between tenure and the basic competencies; and a low, positive correlation between wage and the core competencies.

There was a low, positive correlation between the nature of employment and the qualification of trainers; moderate, negative correlation between tenure and the adequacy of school resources; low, positive correlation between tenure and the trainings attended by the trainers; low, positive correlation between wage and the qualification of trainers; moderate, positive correlation between wage and trainings attended by the trainers.

There was moderate, positive correlation between the nature of employment and the adequacy of school resources; low, positive correlation between the nature of employment and the adequacy of school resources; negligible, negative correlation between tenure and the adequacy of school resources; moderate, positive correlation between tenure and the curriculum of the school; and a negligible, negative correlation between wage and the adequacy of school resources.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Level of competence of trainers needs to be raised to “high level” by encouraging them to pursue graduate studies relevant to their technical baccalaureate preparations and by sending them to relevant trainings local and abroad, as mandated by RA 10912 (Continuing Professional Development Act).
2. Library and other support facilities like medical clinic and sports facilities should be improved. They may not directly affect the level of competence of trainees in cooking but they are equally important in the social, physical and intellectual development of trainees.
3. Blue desk services of the subject schools should be strengthened by establishing active connections with employment agencies like POEA, DOLE, Jobstreet.com and the likes for a wider range of employment opportunities to graduates.
4. Effective tracking of graduates whether employed or not should be implemented by the subject schools to provide possible interventions on improving job-related concerns of graduates.
5. Find out emerging industries competitive to ASEAN.
6. Conduct similar research with a larger, more diverse sample, to confirm the results of this study and improve the generalizations of the results.
7. Conduct researches on employment outcomes of graduates of other TESDA qualifications using other variables.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

I declare that informed consent was obtained and the respondents were given the freedom to withdraw from the study anytime, anonymity of the respondents were maintained, the respondents were not exposed to any form of harm, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results was used purely for research.

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REFERENCES

- Abaida, A., Lakrari, Y., & Abdouni, A. (n.d.). An examination of the relationship between competencies and wages of higher education graduates: Evidence from Morocco. ages of higher education graduates: Evidence from Morocco. *Tuning Journal for Higher Education*. Retrieved from [http://dx.doi.org/10.18543/tjhe-5\(1\)-2017pp75-100](http://dx.doi.org/10.18543/tjhe-5(1)-2017pp75-100)
- Birdir, K., & Pearson, T. E. (2000). Research Chef's Competencies: A Delphi Approach. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 12(3): 205-209, DOI: 10.1108/09596110010309989
- Enright, M. K. & Bejar, I.I. (1998). *An Investigation of the Role of Educational Background on Performance on the GRE Analytical Measure*. Retrieved from http://www.ets.org/research/policy_research_reports/rr-97-17
- Felstead, A. (2011) "Employee involvement, the quality of training and the learning environment: an individual level analysis", *Development and Learning in Organizations: An International Journal*, Vol. 25 Issue: 3, <https://doi.org/10.1108/dlo.2011.08125cad.008>

Loch, C. H., Huberman, B. A., & Stout, S. (2000). Status competition and performance in work groups. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/4933/5a280e445a7924557bb3f50d217905b9670e.pdf>

Skewes L, Fine C, Haslam N (2018) Beyond Mars and Venus: The role of gender essentialism in support for gender inequality and backlash. *PLoS ONE* 13(7): e0200921. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0200921>
